

INTERNATIONAL COMPARISON OF REFRACTOMETRY MEASUREMENTS BETWEEN THE NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF METROLOGY OF MOLDOVA (INM-MD) AND THE UZBEK NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF METROLOGY (UZNIM)

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Abstract. This report presents the results of an international comparison conducted refractometry between the National Institute of Metrology of Moldova (INM-MD) [1] and the Uzbek National Institute of Metrology (UzNIM) in the field of refractometry. The comparison utilized a Certificate Reference Material (CRM) designed for the verification and calibration of refractometers. The aim of the comparison was to demonstrate the metrological and technical competence of the laboratories in determining the refractive index. The measurement results from both laboratories were compared, considering the expanded uncertainty, and the obtained values showed a high degree of consistency between the results of INM-MD and UzNIM. This report highlights the successful completion of the comparison and confirms the laboratories' ability to provide accurate and reliable refractometer calibration results.

Keywords: international comparison, refractometry, Certificate Reference Material, calibration, metrological competence, expanded uncertainty, INM-MD, UzNIM, refractive index, metrology.

Introduction. This report describes the results of international comparison between the two participant INM-MD of Moldova (pilot laboratory) and UzNIM of Uzbekistan were started in September 2023 and finished in March 2025.

The transfer standard was Certificate Reference Material (CRM) in refractometry field. It was agreed that National Institute of Metrology (INM) would be the pilot laboratory for this comparison.

The tasks of the pilot laboratory:

- Prepare the comparison protocol;
- Perform the analysis of the comparison data and elaborate the final report.

The tasks of participant laboratory:

- Perform the measurements according to the rules of this protocol;
- Send to the coordinator comparison results in 15 days after finishing the measurements.

Table 1.

Participants of comparison

№	NMI	Address	Contact person	e-mail address phone, fax
1	National Institute of Metrology (INM-MD)	28, E. Coca Str., Chisinau, Republic of Moldova MD-2064	Ana CURDOV(coordinator)	Tel: (+373) 22 903 100 (+373) 22 903 141 E-mail: info@inm.gov.md fizico.chimice@inm.gov.md
2	Uzbek National Institute of Metrology (UzNIM)	333 A, 333 B, Farobiy street, Almazar district, 100174, Tashkent, Republic of Uzbekistan	Feruza IBRAHIMOV A (responsible for organizational issues)	Tel: +998 (78) 202-00-11 (1209) E-mail: info@nim.uz feruzaig80@gmail.com

Methodology. Outline. Comparison measurements using a CRM are performed to demonstrate metrological and technical competence in the field of refractometry determination.

This bilateral comparison it will be carried out in the context of the technical-scientific collaboration contract between INM and UzNIM, concluded on 11.04.2018.

All information related to this comparison will be officially published in CTŞ (The Scientific Technical Council of INM-MD).

The role of the pilot calibration laboratory is to accompany the process, to give a reference value and to evaluate the measurement results. The methodical approach is according to ISO/IEC 17043:2023. The pilot laboratory will perform a series of measurements using a CRM to ensure the result of the comparative measurement and especially the stability of the transfer standards.

It was agreed that the mean of the measuring results of the INM-MD physico-chemical laboratory will be the reference measuring value for each nominal value [2].

Comparison schedule

Figure 1. Bilateral comparison scheme.

Description of transfer standard

The transfer standard was refractometry CRM 8123-2002, batch:162/23 [4], produced by D. I. Mendeleev Institute for Metrology.

The CRM is intended for testing refractive index measuring instruments, as well as periodic verification and calibration of refractometers. The area of industry and production where the standard sample can be predominantly used: chemical, food and pharmaceutical industries

Table 2.

Comparison Schedule

Start	September 2023
Deadline for the measurement of the INM-MD	May 2024
Deadline for the measurement of the UzNIM	July 2024
Deadline to finalize the results and the draft A report	September 2024
Presentation of the draft A report in the CTS meeting at the CTS of the INM MD	December 2024
Deadline to finalize the results and the final report	March 2025

Table 3.

Refractometry properties of transfer standards, according to the quality control certificates.

Item	Code	Value, (n ^{20D})	Uncertainty (P=0,95)
1.	III-B	1,33299	±0,00002
2.	III-Г	1,38771	±0,00003
3.	III-Ч	1,46023	
4.	III-Б	1,50112	

Calibration method and instrumentation used

All laboratory measurements are performed by direct measurements in accordance with approved calibration procedures. Main characteristics of the method:

Use of a certified reference material (CRM) in the field of refractometry.

Selection of the method of each laboratory in accordance with the approved procedure.

Accounting for auxiliary measuring devices for monitoring environmental conditions.

Reference to the ISO/IEC 17043:2023 standard, which regulates the conduct of interlaboratory comparisons.

Table 4.

INM MD Equipment used

Item	Description	Manufacturer	Model	Serial number	Traceability
1.	Refractometer	Anton Paar, Austria	AbbeMat 550	99076320	INM, Republic of Moldova
2.	Temperature, humidity and pressure indicator	Vaisala, Finland	PTU 301	D3760002	INM, Republic of Moldova

According to an approved calibration procedure, each laboratory selects a calibration method, a formula for calculating measurements, and estimates the expanded uncertainty by multiplying the standard uncertainty by a coverage factor $k = 2$. Expanded uncertainty is used to increase the reliability of measurement results.

Auxiliary measuring instruments are used to measure the ambient conditions.

The technical and metrological characteristics of the standard equipment used in the comparison are presented in table 4 and 5.

Table 5.

UzNIM Equipment used

Item	Description	Manufacturer	Model	Serial number	Traceability
1.	Refractometer	Anton Paar, Austria	Abbemat 550	99076320	INM, Republic of Moldova
2.	Temperature, humidity and pressure indicator	Vaisala, Finland	PTU 301	D3760002	INM, Republic of Moldova

The calibration report should be submitted to the actual environmental conditions during measurement.

Results

The results are presented in table 6 and graphical form at each calibration point.

Table 6.

The results obtained from the measurements

Conventional value		Measured value		Expanded Uncertainty*	
INM-MD	UzNIM	INM-MD	UzNIM	INM-MD	UzNIM
1,33299		1,332984	1,33299	0,000045	0,00002
1,38771		1,387733	1,38775		0,00003
1,46023		1,460227	1,46020		0,00003
1,50112		1,501111	1,50114		0,00003

*Expanded uncertainty corresponding to the coverage probability of approximately 95 %.

Figure 1 shows a device for measuring the refractive index of light in a medium.

Refractometry is an objective measurement of the refraction of the eye using modern specialized equipment. The technique consists in studying the refractive power of the optical system of the eyeball along the longitudinal axis.

Fig. 1. General view of the refractometer

Fig.2. Reference material CRM 8123-2002

Evaluation of comparison measurement

To compare the results, the $|E_n|$ value will be calculated. This value represents the deviation between the results of measurements by the pilot laboratory and the laboratory of the participant, taking into account the uncertainty of the measurement results.

$$|E_n| = \frac{x_{lab} - x_{ref}}{\sqrt{(U_{lab}^2 - U_{ref}^2)}} \quad (1)$$

where:

x_{lab} – the measured value for laboratory of UzNIM;

x_{ref} – the reference value for pilot laboratory (INM-MD);

U_{lab} – calibration expanded uncertainty of UzNIM;

U_{ref} – expanded uncertainty of pilot laboratory (INM-MD).

This value represents the deviation between the measuring results of the participating laboratory and the pilot laboratory under consideration of the measuring uncertainty. For acceptable measurements the value of the $|E_n|$ must be less than 1.

The results of the comparison measurement including E_n -value are summarized in the in the diagram below (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Results of comparison the calibration of INM-MD and UzNIM.

According to ISO/IEC 17043 [3] the determined $|E_n|$ - values of the comparison measurement are ≤ 1 that means the measurement result of INM-MD and UzNIM agree to within the reported expanded uncertainties.

Conclusion. After analyzing the obtained results, it can be seen that the matching factor $|E_n|$ of laboratories participating in the comparisons is in the range $[-1; +1]$.

Thus, the laboratories participating in the bilateral comparisons have demonstrated their competence and their capabilities in the field of calibrating refractometer, and their results are considered positive.

REFERENCES

1. The National Institute of Metrology of Moldova (INM-MD)
2. INM-MD physico-chemical laboratory
3. ISO/IEC 17043:2023 «Conformity assessment — General requirements for the competence of proficiency testing providers».
4. CRM 8123-2002, batch: 162/23